

Popular Article

Prevention and control of Piglet Anemia

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Abstract

The swine industry is extremely significant in India's north-east and other regions. Since pigs are primarily raised for their flesh, it is important to take good care of them, especially before and after farrowing. Farm profits rise as a result of it. Amongst which, piglet care is essential to averting piglet anaemia caused by low iron levels in sow milk. Because of its lethal nature this illness, the pig industry suffers tremendous losses. Therefore, to combat this issue, an oral and injectable iron supplement must be given to piglets on their fourth and fourteenth days of life.

Keywords: Piglet, iron, milk, farrowing.

Introduction

Piglets are light brown in colour and have fluid around their internal organs, chest, and throat. Numerous illnesses and disorders could affect and harm them. Anaemia is responsible for around 10% of mortality prior to untreated waste weaning. Since pig farmers started throwing waste into their confinement areas, depriving suckling pigs access to the ground, paediatric anaemia has become a significant issue.

Haemoglobin, a protein that makes up around one-third of the weight of red blood cells, contains iron, which is a critical element. The special role of red blood haemoglobin is to carry oxygen from the lungs to the body's tissues to promote cellular metabolism and to return the carbon metabolism that results to the lungs. The piglet cannot assimilate enough haemoglobin in the absence of iron shortage. Baby pig anaemia, a disorder in which the blood's ability to carry oxygen is significantly decreased, is typically brought on by a deficiency of iron.

Aetiology

Due to the following factors, iron deficiency develops faster:

1. Limited iron retention in the piglet.
2. Decreased iron levels in colostrum and milk.
3. The loss of contact iron from the soil.
4. The breeding pig's faster growth.
5. Insufficient storage of iron in the piglet.

New born pigs are born with a total of 50 mg of iron in their bodies, the majority of which is contained in the bloodstream and liver in the form of haemoglobin. A normal developing new born need roughly 7 mg of iron per day to maintain blood haemoglobin levels, thus 1 mg is taken orally or with milk during feeding. during the gestation phase, only 35 to 50 mg of iron is transferred per piglet from the sow, new born piglets have low iron reserves (**Szabo and Bilkei, 2002; Venn *et al*, 1947**).

Pigs that are lactating grow much faster. A piglet has a greater capacity for growth than other domestic mammals. Due to the pig's rapid development and rising plasma volume, a substantial iron intake is necessary to maintain optimal haemoglobin levels.

Clinical Signs and Symptoms

Anaemia caused by iron deficiency can range from mild to severe. Poor development, decreased appetite, coarse hair, wrinkled skin, and painful mucous membranes are all symptoms of chronic anaemia.

The most typical sign of severe anaemia is discomfort in breathing, also known as "thumps", which are caused due to contractions of the diaphragm muscles post exercise. In the worst instance, pigs that grow rapidly could abruptly pass away from respiratory failure. Additionally, anaemia lowers the pig's tolerance to illnesses and respiratory issues. Chronic pigs are more prone to enteritis. Enlargement of the heart and spleen, fluid in the chest and belly, and lower blood pressure are all signs of necropsy detection in anaemic pigs. Furthermore, the mucous membranes are visible.

Diagnoses

During an autopsy, unprocessed blood samples and smears are examined to determine whether a piglet is anaemic.

Treatment

To inject extra iron by injections, oral administration, or other methods. Pigs often obtain adequate iron in their diet once they are weaned.

Oral

Natural iron that has been prepared with iron galactan and given to pigs before 18 hours of birth prevents several issues associated with iron injections. However, maintenance is costly. Because iron galactan is only absorbed in the intestines at a very young age, much like colostrum, pigs should be immunised within 18 hours of birth. Pigs should get the entire daily dosage and a follow-up dose when the

initial dose needs to be refilled. When pigs are flooded, it is not advisable to use this procedure since digestion might not function well. After 18 hours, switch to a different preparation strategy.

Incorporate copper sulphate (5 mg) and ferrous sulphate (25 mg) in trace amounts into the pork diet or water. Piglets can be given artificial iron by mouth to avoid anaemia. Repeated dosing is needed since a significant fraction is absorbed through the abdomen wall every day.

Chemicals like ferrous sulphate are less expensive but demand more time, effort, and dosages.

Injections

Piglets are frequently supplemented by being injected with iron dextran, iron galactan, or other iron derivatives.

Before the piglets are 72 hours old, the immunisation is typically administered. Apply it to the muscles or underneath the skin as per the manufacturer's directions. Before use, disinfect the injection site as well as the needles and syringes. Utilize a proper hypodermic needle gauge to prevent excess leakage at the injection site. Pigs frequently sustain injuries at the site of injection, and injections into the leg may result in paralysis, raising the risk of unintentional pig bites.

Iron Deficiency Anaemia Prevention

Piglets' needs for more iron can be satisfied in a variety of methods, which are:

1. Orally
2. By parenteral route (through injection).

These nutrients initially manifest as plasma iron (transferrin), which is carried from the bone marrow to the formation of red cell haemoglobin, to the muscle's myoglobin, which helps with the conversion of muscular tissue, and to the liver's iron enzyme required for cellular modification. Myoglobin and haemoglobin can both be made from injectable muscle-dextran, which is absorbed from the muscles by adjacent lymph nodes and delivered into the bloodstream.

Oral

Oral administration of iron is not so useful in iron deficiency anaemia, Often, though, during peroral administration, piglets do not get the intended dose of iron (**Svoboda et al, 2005**)

Soil

This is a useful method for supplying iron when the soil is dynamic and free of swine parasite eggs. If the creep floor is slightly divided, apply the soil on the solid part of the pen concrete. Put the soil on a little tray once the creep floor is smooth. The workers' involvement and difficulty locating the land on which the land is located are drawbacks of this strategy.

Parenteral method

Injections can also be used to manage the additional iron needed to prevent anaemia. Due to the prevention of anaemia caused by iron deficiency in new born piglets, there is, worldwide, routine application of a single parenteral administration in the form of an iron dextran injection (200 mg Fe³⁺) when piglets are 2-4 days old (Sun *et al*, 2006).

Conclusion

It has been observed that in the pig industry, piglets are protected from anaemia during the first few months of life because iron deficiency in sow milk results in piglet death. piglets with iron administered at birth had significantly higher haematological values and better production performance than piglets which did not receive iron, and which subsequently developed anaemia. Subcutaneous injection of iron was the most effective administration method, resulting in highest levels of iron, haemoglobin and PCV in piglet blood, and consequently the best productive performances. Therefore, it is essential to keep the piglet away from developing anaemia in order to increase the piggery industry's profit.

References

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